
PUBLIC SECTOR MANAGEMENT AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: EVIDENCE FROM NDIC

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ABSTRACT

The public sector is usually a stronghold for the economy, but recently in Nigeria, the sector has faced many hiccups due to neglect and poor management. The financial sector had its challenges ranging from instability to unsafe banking systems resulting in loss of depositors' confidence among others. The government managed the situation by establishing the Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) which is a parastatal under the Nigerian Ministry of Finance to supervise insured banks, among other roles. This study, therefore, examined NDIC- a public sector organization to ascertain its contribution to Sustainable Development (SD) in Nigeria. A survey method was used. The population comprised 25 insured Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. Purposive sampling was used in selecting a sample size of 16 insured DMBs. Data were collected from a primary source through a questionnaire. Descriptive statistics were employed in data analyses while Ordinary Least Square (OLS) pooled regression and Two-Stage Least Square regression analyses were employed to obtain the estimates for hypotheses testing. A Durbin-Wu-Hausman test was employed to find out Endogeneity in OLS regression. Findings revealed that the effectiveness of NDIC in achieving SD in Nigeria is significant but the efficiency and economic impact of NDIC in achieving sustainable development are not significant. The study concluded that NDIC has effectively facilitated SD but has efficiently and economically failed. The study has made an expository impact on how public sector organizations can be utilized effectively to cushion the activities of the private sector enterprises to achieve SD.

Keywords: Public Sector Management, Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation, Insured Deposit Money Banks, Sustainable Development.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The public sector is the grouping of entities in complete ownership and control of the government to deliver products or services at affordable prices to the citizens (Aminu & Nuhu, 1999; Ogohi, 2014). The public sector enterprises have faced a lot of criticism for obvious reasons (Okeke, Onuorah & Okonkwo, 2016). One of the major criticisms is that since the public sector lacks private interests and competition, there is always neglect which persistently breeds inefficiency where so much was utilized to achieve too little. In Africa and most developing countries of the world, neglects and dilapidation of public-sector enterprises have continued to reoccur. Nigeria is a case in hand where these enterprises were managed to the point of liquidation. All attempts to deliver quality services to the people through public enterprises failed. The establishment of Ajaokuta Steel Company, Nigerian Refineries, Nigerian Cotton Mills, National Electric Power Authority (NEPA), National Water Board, Nigerian Railways, Nigerian Telecommunication Limited (NITEL), and whole lots of others became abysmal failures. The unsuccessfulness of these government-established enterprises authenticated the view that government has no business doing business (Okeke, et al. 2016; Ali, 2021). The policymakers in Nigeria contemplated that the private sector would do better, thereby aligning with the thoughts of the free-market system where the forces of the market determine the demand and supply of goods and services in an economy. This was the rationale behind the commercialization of most public enterprises in Nigeria between 1985 and 1995 and finally privatization between 1999 and 2010. Areas that received tremendous attention through commercialization and privatization include; electricity, telecommunication and energy.

The question is, can the free-market enterprise be effective in countries like Nigeria where close substitutes for products or services are not available? What was witnessed after the exercise became exploitation of the highest magnitude because the state of the sectors in terms of quality delivery to the people remained the same and even worse except for the telecommunication industry due to the evolution of the mobile communication system (Okeke, et al. 2016). The people were faced with no option but to receive haphazardly delivered products or services at higher costs. Sometimes where the alternative is seen to be close; it did look like facing the devil and the red sea which should be unacceptable to anyone in good senses. The situation became counter-productive and quite obvious that the clamour for a completely free market system cannot work in the interest of the people of Nigeria.

It could be recalled in line with the economic history that a completely free-market system had failed in advanced economies like Great Britain, causing the great economic depression of the 1930s. Keynes theorized and demonstrated how irresponsible government could be by leaving the economy to operate unguided (Bhatia, 1999). Government must through its agencies make policies (amidst others) to create enabling environment for free-market enterprise so that it would enhance the quality delivery of goods and services to the people at affordable prices. Situations where the entire economy is left to be directed by Adam Smith's "invincible" hands often result in either market failure for well-established economies or exploitation for developing economies.

Banks in Nigeria operated under the Banks and other Financial Institutions Acts (2020) as amended (BOFIA) and the guidelines of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). Banks, no doubt, represent every economy's useful tool for sustainable development because a well-developed and appropriately functioning banking system is necessary for the effectiveness of all economies. Banks through the facilitation of the monetary process by accepting deposits and making the same available to investors have become huge enhancers of sustainable development. There is hardly any well-developed economy whose financial sector is not

strong. Banks all over the world are major players in the financial sector. In Nigeria, banks are grouped under the organized private sector. This would mean that banks are propelled by a profit motive, as long as; their activities do not contravene the BOFIA and the CBN guidelines. With all intents directed towards profit, banking operations had resulted in huge losses for the depositors who were scarcely protected by the government and the banks themselves. Many banks were liquidated between 1980 and 1988 because the banks were involved in a lot of unguided investments which culminated in too many non-performing loans (Amadi, Adetiloye, Babajide, & Amadi, 2021) which gulped depositors' funds and upon those bank liquidations, the depositors were scarcely indemnified. It became clear that the fate of the depositors can no longer be left to be determined by the profit-making derive of the businessmen lest the Nigerian financial sector should be devastated beyond any known economic remedy. Policymakers had read the handwriting on the wall that stakeholders had started losing confidence in the Nigerian banking system. There cannot be a financial sector without a dependable banking system. How can the banking system be dependable when depositors' funds are not protected? Wadesango, Nkhambala, Sitsha and Malatji (2021) pointed out that depositors' fund is a major source of funding for the banks. Depositors need to be re-assured that their money is safe and thus the need for the establishment of a policy-driven organization like the Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) by the federal government of Nigeria.

Banks are an undeniably great tool for sustainable development (Rosella, 2018) but the banking system must be dependable. The dependability of the banking system should be a strong factor in determining the financial stability of a country which in turn enhances sustainable development (Babajide, Lawal, Okafor & Osuma, 2020). This study evaluated the management of NDIC as a public sector organization in line with the broad objective of enhancing stability in the banking system to achieve sustainable development. The study specifically: Determined the Effectiveness of NDIC in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria; Ascertained the Efficiency of NDIC in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria and Examined the Economic impact of NDIC in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria.

Hypotheses formulated to guide the study were as stated in their null form below:

- The Effectiveness of NDIC in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria is not significant.
- The Efficiency of NDIC in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria is not significant.
- The Economic impact of NDIC in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria is not significant.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

The public Sector

The public is the concern of everyone. The word "public" is derived from the Latin word "publicus" meaning "of the people of the state, common or ordinary". All activities targeted at public interest, therefore, are focused on benefitting the majority of the people. The public sector of an economy is the sector that offers a range of governmental services which includes; infrastructure, public transportation, public education, health care, police, and military services. The nature of these services has compelled scholars to refer to them as public or social goods: the topmost ranking reason advanced by these scholars is that it is difficult for a member of the public to acquire the quantity and quality one needed of them. Kent State University (2018) defines the public sector as a part of the nation's economy

which is attached to public programs or services and managed by the government. It possesses the features such as; public interest, public good provision, legal backing, public funding, and government control.

Public Sector Organizations

Adams, (2006) defines public sector organizations as every organization, which is owned/established and operated by the government on behalf of the public. Conceptually, we adopt the categorization of Kent State University (2018) to segmentalize entities under the public sector organizations as follows; (a) core government agencies and departments i.e. executives, legislature or judicial branches of national, state, or local governments, (b) agencies that supply public programs, goods or services but exist a separate organization apart from the one in (a), (c) public entities and non-profit organizations which are similar to governments agencies distribute programs, goods or services, however, are not dependent on the government and may have their source(s) of revenues as well as being funded by the public. The driven economic force lacking in public sector organizations is "private interest" and for this singular reason, it is not profit-driven.

Reasons for Public Sector Organizations

The point of emphasis in the world today is self-determination, getting people to be responsible for their own lives. Partly for this and partly for efficiency of resource use, globalization and liberalization have become the new world order since the start of the 21st century. Capitalist economies have advanced the efficiency of the "invincible hands" in the production and allocation of goods and services in a market-oriented economy. The entire world has come to terms with the practice of free-market mechanism and the World Trade Organization (WTO) today, under the leadership of Professor Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala, promotes trade liberalization (Iloh, Nwokedi, Onyebukwa & Ekeocha, 2021) and; the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank most often ascertain the level of liberalization of an economy acceptable to them before extending financial assistance to such economy. This has compelled the economy of countries to liberalize state-owned enterprises into privatized and commercialized enterprises to follow in the world order. With all the privatization and commercialization efforts by countries of the world, there are still many public sector organizations existing in many economies, even among the very advanced and fast-growing economies like the United States of America, Great Britain, Japan, Taiwan, and China et cetera. Nigeria's economy has undergone several stages of liberalization practices in the last few decades. Several restrictions were removed to privatize some public sector enterprises and other restrictions were relaxed to accommodate the commercialization of some public sector enterprises. The Nigerian Deposit Insurance Co-operation has maintained its public sector-organization status despite its enhancing characteristic to function as a private organization just like every other insurance company in the country. There is no single country in the world that has privatized or commercialized all its vital public sector organizations. Why has it been impossible for countries of the world to eliminate all their public sector organizations?

Musgrave and Musgrave (1989) advanced market failure as a major reason why there is a need for public sector organizations. Explaining further they opined that only market mechanisms cannot execute the entire fiscal functions, thereby, emphasizing the need for public policy which should guide, correct and supplement market mechanism in certain respects. Public sector organizations are simply indispensable in the modern economy due to increased governmental roles and the need to be part of the world order for sustainable development goals (SDGs). Modern governments have gone beyond the traditional roles of

maintaining laws and orders to assume expanded roles which include; welfare activities, job creation, stimulation of private investments, redistribution of income, etc. (Ohachosim, 2017).

Public Sector Management (PSM)

Public Sector Management entails a range of activities involving planning, formulating, and implementing policies, programs, and projects used by the government in delivering goods and services to the nation/state (Adams, 2006).

Three E's of Public Sector Management (Effectiveness, Efficiency, Economy)

Effectiveness, Efficiency, and Economy are the 3 important constituents of good public sector management. These three E's of public sector management implies that various organizations entrusted with the responsibility of managing and controlling public resources should execute these roles and render services to the public in an effective, economic and efficient manner (Adams, 2006). Effectiveness: Getting the expected results from the output (or doing the right thing). Efficiency: Getting the most from the inputs (or getting a lot from the effort). Economy: Getting the right inputs at the lowest cost (or getting a good deal)

Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is a thought that provides that human beings should live and meet their needs without compromising the ability of the generations to come in providing their own needs (Brandtland Report, 1987). Sustainable development can be achieved if the government can through public sector organizations cushion the activities of private sector organizations towards sustainable development goals (SDGs). Countries of the world make efforts to be part of the United Nation's 2030 agenda for sustainable development goals (UNO, 2015).

The Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation

The Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) is a public sector organization established to enhance sustainable development through the stabilization of the financial system by protecting Nigerian Depositors. It was established in 1989 (under Decree no. 22, 1988) following the recommendations of a committee set up by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) board in 1983 to examine the operations of Nigerian banks. Presently, decree No. 22 of 1988 has been replaced by NDIC Act No.16 of 2006, which contains the functions, funding and governance of NDIC (Federal Republic of Nigeria, Official Gazette, 2006).

NDIC and Sustainable Development

Badar, Changiun, Changhui and Ningyu (2020) observed that explicit deposit insurance causes capital regulations on banking risk during turbulent economic situations. Similarly, Ningyu, Kezhong, Chagium and Badar (2019) found that when there are rivals among banks, they involve in huge risks takings which unequivocal deposit insurance system may not be efficient in preventing. Denzi, Asli and Min (2014) stated that deposit insurance corporation promotes financial system stability as they reduce the depositors' incentives in monitoring banks and by this, take lots of risks.

Theoretical Review

This study was anchored on Keynes' theory. The theory was propounded by Lord Maynard Keynes in 1936. Keynes' general theory explained among other things that governmental role, through the public sector organizations, are pivotal due to their ability to utilize policies to direct and re-direct the economy towards desired and sustainable goals. Keynes theorized that

it was irresponsibility on the part of a modern government to allow changes to occur in the economy without interference. This was the birth of a mixed economy which is practised by all the economies of the world today. The summary implication of Keynes general theory is the positioning of government to provide the necessary stimulation for the required economic activities, be it employment, interest and money, as well as, goods and services. Government can achieve this by relying on one or all of these; taxation, government spending and policy options.

This study relied on Keynes's general theory for the explanation of the need for the public sector organizations like the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC). Public sector organizations are indispensable to foresee market failure and re-adjust policies to prevent it, provide social goods, achieve other social goals, as well as, provide useful advice on policy formulation for effective functioning of the economy.

Empirical Review

Okolie and Ikenga (2024) using analytical method, secondary data and content analysis, found that top government officials and political office holders in public sector entities find it very grave to make government employees to behave ethically at all times.

Ugoani (2024) using an exploratory investigation literature review research design, found a significant positive association between the new public management and governance sustainability.

Ofodile (2023) used the library research technique and found that it is necessary to accelerate the implementation of the sustainable development goals from the public administration and governance perspective to ensure sustainability.

Chidi-Okeke, Chukwu, Chris-Ejiogu and Ositadimma (2021) found a negative and insignificant effect of public expenditure on human development index.

Nwanyanwu, Igbara and Njoku (2020) evaluated the operations of NDIC on bank performance in Nigeria. The study concluded that the NDIC operations have improved public confidence in the banking system by protecting depositors' funds and have also increased the profitability of the banks. The study suggested that the NDIC should extend its coverage to shareholders and other non-bank financial institutions as this will ensure the overall stability of the financial system.

Gichuru (2018) studied the economy of Kenya with the roles of the public sector and enlisting too many failed impressions of the free market system. The study is qualitative and adopted the content analyses in its deductive arguments. The study found that public-private partnerships must be employed to achieve sustainable development.

Alinska, Filipiak, and Kosztowiak (2018) studied the importance of the public sector in sustainable development in Poland. Data on the selected variables covered the period 1995-2018. The study employed econometric modelling and analyses to generate both descriptive and inferential statistics. The evaluation of these results identified the need for a special alliance between the public and financial sector of the Poland economy. It recommended that government should correct the existing public policies and utilize expenditure instruments and profitable public instruments.

Okeke, Onuorah and Okonkwo (2016) carried out a massive literature review on public enterprises in Nigeria and the privatization option. The review emphasized that though the public sector has faced a lot of challenges, privatization should not be seen as an end solution. The paper advocated for a public-private partnership to drive home quality to the consumers whose concerns revolve around quantity, quality and price.

Chukwuemeka, Okechukwu, and Iloanya (2015) in the study titled "the dwindling performance of the public organization in Nigeria: the role of corporate governance" evaluated the performance of public organizations in Nigeria. The study employed a questionnaire and interview for the data gathering and applied the spearman's rank correlation for data analyses. The study established that corporate governance mechanisms in Enugu state public organizations do not match the established standards. The study recommends that those in charge of corporate governance should carry out their duties devoid of fear or favour.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

A survey design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 25 insured Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria and the sample size was arrived at 16 being the number of insured DMBs operating in Anambra State (CBN, 2025; NDIC, 2025). Primary data obtained through questionnaires were used. The questionnaire was structured on a continuum 5-1 Likert Scale and was administered to any senior officer (from the rank of manager) of the sampled banks in Anambra State. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics and the estimates for the test of hypotheses were obtained by employing the methods of Ordinary Least Square (OLS) pooled regression and 2-stage Least Square regression analyses. OLS was relied upon for the regression estimates because it is known for possessing estimates with minimal variance (Koutsoyiannis, 1997; Gujarati & Porter, 2004). A Durbin-Wu-Hausman test was employed to find out Endogeneity in OLS regression. Relevant estimates of the regression were interpreted for the attained conclusion. Analyses were performed at a 5% level of significance.

Model Specification

The study posits that sustainable development (SD) is a function of Public Sector Management (PSM). The Public Sector Management was evaluated relying on three yardsticks; Public Sector Management Effectiveness (EFTV), Public Sector Management Efficiency (EFCY), and Public Sector Management Economy (ECMY). The model on which the regression analysis was performed in this study is built on the reviewed theory and followed thus;

$$SD = F(\text{PSM}) \dots\dots\dots 1 \text{ (FUNCTIONAL FORM)}$$

$$SD = F(\text{EFTV}, \text{EFCY}, \text{ECMY}) \text{ ----- } 1 \text{ (EXPANDED FUNCTIONAL FORM)}$$

$$SD = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{EFTV} + \beta_2 \text{EFCY} + \beta_3 \text{ECMY} + \mu_0 \text{ ----- } 2 \text{ (ECONOMETRIC FORM)}$$

Where: SD = Sustainable Development, PSM = Public Sector Management, EFTV= Effectiveness, EFCY = Efficiency and ECMY= Economy

Measurement of Variables in the Model

Relevant questions were asked to assess the presence of the presumed qualities in the variables. The values of the variables are all functions of the weights of the responses to the questions designed on a Likert scale of 5-1. Four questions were asked to measure the value

of SD. Two questions each were asked to measure the values of EFTV, EFCY and ECMY. Therefore,

$$SD = WRD_1 + \dots + WRD_4$$

$$EFTV = WRV_1 + WRV_2$$

$$EFCY = WRC_1 + WRC_2$$

$$ECMY = WRM_1 + WRM_2$$

$$\begin{matrix} SD & EFTV & EFCY & ECMY \\ (WRD_{1.1} + \dots + WRD_{1.4}) = & (WRV_{1.1} + WRV_{1.2}), & (WRC_{1.1} + WRC_{1.2}), & (WRM_{1.1} + WRM_{1.2}) \text{ obs. (1)} \end{matrix}$$

$$\begin{matrix} (WRD_{2.1} + \dots + WRD_{2.4}) = & (WRV_{2.1} + WRV_{2.2}), & (WRC_{1.1} + WRC_{2.2}), & (WRM_{2.1} + WRM_{2.2}) \text{ obs. (2)} \\ * & * & * & * \\ * & * & * & * \\ * & * & * & * \end{matrix}$$

$$(WRD_{16.1} + \dots + WRD_{16.4}) = (WRV_{16.1} + WRV_{16.2}), (WRC_{16.1} + WRC_{16.2}), (WRM_{16.1} + WRM_{16.2}) \text{ obs. (16)}$$

Where; WRD1 = weight of response 1 on SD, WRD4 = weight of response 4 on SD, WRV1 = weight of response 1 on EFTV, WRV2 = weight of response 2 on EFTV, WRC1 = weight of response 1 on EFCY, WRC2 = weight of response 2 on EFCY, WRM1 = weight of response 1 on ECMY and WRM2 = weight of response 2 on ECMY.

The suffixes; 1.1 denotes Bank 1, response 1; 1.2 denotes bank 1 response 2; 16.1 denotes bank 16, response 1; 16.2 denotes bank 16, response 2 and 16.4 denotes bank 16, response 4.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The researchers succeeded in getting a high-ranking officer of each bank (as stipulated in the methodology) to respond to the questionnaire. The questionnaire was, therefore, distributed and collected 100%.

Table 4.1 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
eftv	16	6.8125	2.428134	3	10
efcy	16	6.625	2.334524	3	10
ecmy	16	6.875	2.276694	3	10
sd	16	15.75	4.09064	8	20

Source: Analysis Output (2025) using STATA ver. 14

The descriptive statistics of table 4.1 shows that NDIC possesses high management profile and has enhanced sustainable development (SD) by ensuring stability in the banking system of Nigeria. This is inferred from the values of the mean scores of the public sector management proxies; eftv, efty, and ecmy which are; 6.8125, 6.625, and 6.875 respectively. These scores tilt towards the Maximum values of 10 in each case showing that NDIC scores are very significantly above average. Also with the mean score of 15.75 for SD, the researchers inferred that the stability of the banking system achieved so far in Nigeria is likely to be sustained in the continuous presence of the NDIC. The standard deviation of 2.428134, 2.334524, 2.276694, and 4.098664 for eftv, efty, and ecmy and SD is glaring evidence of outliers which is in the real sense of its reservations (areas to be improved in NDIC). This of course should contribute to low sustainability. On a holistic evaluation of the descriptive statistics, the researchers are of the view that all the NDIC-insured banks believe that NDIC has high profile management (acceptable standard) and that has enhanced stability in the banking system in Nigeria.

Regression Analysis

An OLS pooled regression and a two-stage least square regression are included in this table to analyze the cause-and-effect correlations between SD and PSM and in testing the hypotheses that have been developed.

Table 4.2: Regression Results

	SD Model (Pooled OLS)	SD Model (2Stage Least Square)
C	6.37 {0.008} **	6.37 {0.000} ***
EFTV	1.56 {0.005}**	1.56 {0.000} ***
EFCY	-0.43 {0.293}	-0.43 {0.204}
ECMY	0.23 {0.611}	0.23 {0.547}
F-statistics/Wald Statistics	11.73 (0.001) **	46.91 (0.00) ***
R- Squared	0.75	0.75
VIF Test	2.83	
Heteroscedasticity Test	0.71 (0.4007)	
Endogeneity Test	4.77 (0.0464) **	

Note: (1) bracket {} are p-values

(2) **, *, implies statistical significance at 5% and 1% levels respectively**

Source: Analysis Output (2025) using STATA ver. 14

Table 4.2 reveals that the R-squared value for the OLS pooled regression is 0.75, which means the independent variables explained nearly 75% of the systematic variance in sustainable development in the pooled banks over time. The remaining 25% which could have an impact on sustainable development are reflected in the error term which may be blamed for the unexplained portion of sustainable development. There was a statistically significant F-statistic of 11.73 and its' related P-value of 0.001, which indicates that the overall OLS regression model is valid and may be used for statistical inference at a 5% level of significance. Furthermore, a mean VIF of 2.83 is within the benchmark value of 10, indicating that there is no multicollinearity, and so no independent variables should be deleted from the model. OLS results exhibited no heteroscedasticity issues because the probability values are not significant at 1% or 5% [0.71 (0.4007)] from the table above. A correlation between the error term and the right-hand explanatory variable should be impossible in theory, and this test reveals if there is a correlation. As a result, a Durbin-Wu-Hausman test is employed to find out endogeneity in OLS regression. Endogeneity is a major issue in our OLS model, and according to Durbin-Wu Hausman test statistics in table 4.2 above, it is 4.77 (0.0464).

Our variables are linked to the error term because of the presence of endogeneity. The 2Stage Least Square regression was therefore used to account for this effect (Zaefarian et al., 2017). The Wald-statistic score of 46.91 (0.00) suggests that the model is valid for making inferences because it is statistically significant at 1%. As measured by R-squared, 75% of the variation in sustainable development can be explained by independent variables, which is consistent with previous research. The two-stage least square regression is used to perform a detailed examination of each of the independent variables.

Discussion of Findings

The first result of this study is in line with the work of Nwanyanwu, Igbara and Njoku (2020) that NDIC has been very effective in stabilizing the banking system by bringing back depositors' confidence. The Effectiveness of NDIC in achieving sustainable development appears significant and positive (2Stage Least Square regression = 1.56 (0.000)) as a separate variable. This, therefore, means rejecting the first null hypothesis (H_{01}) and accepting the alternate hypothesis that the effectiveness of NDIC in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria is significant. This finding authenticates Keynes's general theory which emphasized that government should guide the economy to avoid possible market failure (Bhatia, 1997). Government guidelines emerge from its agencies (public sector organizations) in the form of policies. NDIC represents the government to guide the banks to ensure that depositors' funds are protected and the banking system stabilized. The attainment of this goal implies that the public sector organization can enhance sustainable development in Nigeria. It is further in agreement with recent studies that established the effectiveness of public-private partnerships in the economy (Okeke, Onuorah & Okonkwo, 2016; Gichuru, 2018; Alinsk, Filipiak & Kosztowiak, 2018). The essence of the partnership is for the government to control the excesses associated with the private sector among others. However, the second result on Efficiency of NDIC (2Stage Least Square regression = -0.43 (0.204)) appears to have a negative and minor effect on sustainable development as an independent variable. This, therefore, means accepting the second null hypothesis (H_{02}) that the Efficiency of NDIC in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria is not significant. This suggests that NDIC is lacking efficiency in the use of resources even though the desired goal is achieved and this has decreasing effects on sustainable development. The Nigerian public sector was often criticized for gross inefficiencies. Proponents of the free-market system have adduced all forms of inefficiency in the public sector to a lack of private interests. Studies by Abukadir and Olashide (2018) and Mustapha (2022) attributed inefficiency in Nigeria's public sector to the presence of high-level corruption. Finally, the third result shows evidence that NDIC is also lacking in the economy of acquisition of resources (2Stage Least square regression = 0.23 (0.547)). Economy has a positive and non-significant effect on sustainable development. This implies accepting the third null hypothesis (H_{03}). This finding is not uncommon in Nigeria's public sector where costs of procurement are regularly inflated by greedy personnel. In line with this Okotie and Tafamel (2020) deduced that lack of transparency is the cause of the high cost of procurement in the public sector in Nigeria. This will surely have a decreasing effect on sustainable development.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study examined the Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC), a public sector organization, in terms of how its management has helped in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. Findings revealed that although NDIC has brought some improvements in the Nigerian banking system through the restoration of depositors' confidence, and a stable and sustainable banking system, which implies that it has achieved the goal for which it was established, it has not significantly contributed to sustainable development in Nigeria when evaluated on the yardsticks of its efficiency and economy criteria. Based on this, the study concluded that public sector management evaluated on its effectiveness is significant in achieving sustainable development in Nigeria but not on its efficiency and economic impact. The researchers, therefore, recommended that public sector organizations like NDIC should not relent in their responsibilities but should as well strive to make the best uses of their resources which must be acquired at the lowest possible costs. The personnel of such organizations should be regularly sponsored for local and international

training/seminars/workshops to keep them abreast with international best practices on public sector organization management.

Contributions of the study

Theoretical contributions

Several works have expanded the coverage of Keynes' general theory. David & Eric, (2021), Stieglitz (2021), Jeffrey (2020) and Boyd (1988) have pointed out that the government's pivotal roles include piloting private sectors through government policies' desired goals. This work is a step further to strengthening this base theory through the use of NDIC which cushions banks' operations as it relates to depositors' funds.

Practical implication

A major practical implication of this work is its expository capacity which revealed that public sector organizations like the NDIC are necessary to moderate the excesses of most privately owned organizations in Nigeria.

Social Implication

The study has demonstrated that the use of public sector organizations like NDIC has prevented dubious bank directors from duping the depositors thereby reducing the level of crime in the banking system and restoring depositors' confidence.

Limitations of the Study

The result of this study cannot be generalized to all sectors of the Nigerian economy. The study covered the banks which are professionalized service providers. Similar research for manufacturing/ other firms may give a different result and this is subject to further studies.

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